

PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS (PCA) OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES THAT AFFECT THE EXTENT OF LINKAGE AND CO-ORDINATION AMONG STAKEHOLDERS FOR EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF WATERSHED DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME

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Abstract

The watershed management implies for the judicious use of all the resources i.e. land, water and vegetation in an area for providing an answer to alleviate drought, moderate floods, prevent soil erosion, improve water availability and crop productivity on sustained basis and this programme aims to achieve maximum production with minimum hazard to the natural resources and for the well being of people. The present study was conducted with a sample size of 192 progressive farmers and watershed user groups in Nuapada and Kalahandi district of Odisha state, aiming to identify the major socio economic factors governing extent of linkages and involvements, and coordination among the water user groups with different stake holders and developmental departments involved in implementation of different watershed activities. It is evident from the study that socioeconomic factors such as land holding, annual income, type of house, cosmo-politeness and extension contact, Education, use communication materials, social participation and age of the farmers, can be associated with higher level of linkage and coordination. Three different principal components (PCs) could finally be extracted out of twelve relatively important variables governing functional linkage and establishment of good coordination and participation level of farmers. According to the this study three main factors identified were "big and progressive farmers", "education and extension contact" and "farming occupation" which have been found as significant factors in influencing the functional linkage, liaison and co ordination among the stake holders and these principal components contributed 23.52%, 19.99%, and 13.81% variance in determining the extent of farmers' functional linkage and co ordination level with other stake holders and these three components accounting for 57.33% of the total variability. It was concluded that these factors can be used as essential input to predict models or as benchmarks for developing scales or indices for measuring farmers' active associations and involvement in watershed activities.

Key words- Watershed development programme, Socio economic factors, functional linkages and co-ordination, Principal Components Analysis.

Introduction

Soil, water, vegetation and energy are the basic natural resources needed for agricultural production. It is an established fact that conservation of natural resources and their management holds key to sustainable agriculture. Watershed Management is necessary to protect, conserve and improve the land resource for efficient and sustained production, to protect and enhance water resource, conserve rain water and increase irrigation for crops, thus the programme aims to mitigate drought as well as utilize the natural resources at optimum level for improving agriculture and allied occupation or industries (small and cottage industries) to improve socio-economic conditions of the local residents. Watershed Development Programme has been conceptualized as the rational utilization of land and water resources for optimum and sustained production with minimum hazard to natural resources. The goal of watershed management is to protect or conserve the hydrologic services the watershed provides while minimising or avoiding adverse downstream or groundwater impacts. Watershed management is the integrated use of land, vegetation, and water in a geographically discrete drainage area for the benefit of its residents (Darghouth et al., 2008). The Watershed management implies the judicious use of the resources i.e. land, water and vegetation in an area for improving an answer to alleviate drought, moderate floods, prevent soil erosion, improve water availability as well as increase food, fodder, fuel and fiber on sustained basis. Watershed has to achieve maximum production with minimum hazard to the natural resources and for the well being of people. The main objective of the watershed approach is to minimize adverse effects of drought on the production of crops, livestock's and productivity of land to promote overall economic development as well as improve the socio-economic conditions of the resource poor and disadvantaged sections of inhabitants. Watershed is defined as a geographic area drained by stream or a system of connecting streams in such a manner that all surface run off originating due to the precipitation in the area leaves the area in a concentrated flow through a single outlet (Singh, 2000). Watershed management has been defined as "Rational Utilization of Land and

Water Resources for optimum and sustain production with a minimum hazard to natural resources" (Osterman, 1988). In fact, watershed development has become the main intervention for natural resource management which means proper land use, protecting land against all forms of degradation, building and maintaining soil fertility, proper management of rainwater, flood protection, draught mitigation and increasing productivity from all land uses.

Watershed Development Programme aimed at the development of the watershed as a whole. The beneficiaries having land may get the benefits from the Agriculture, Horticulture and Soil Conservation Departments. The landless people need the support of animal Resource and other departments. Linkage with traders and input dealers ensure timely supply of inputs, credit institutions for financial assistance, research institute for capacity building and technology generation, cooperation department for subsidy and marketing of the produce, Agriculture Engineering for farm mechanization, revenue department for plantations and fodder development in Government land for the landless and resource poor as well as electricity department for power supply towards farm activities. It is therefore suggested that the project officials have to liason with all these departments and establish good linkage for adequate support ensuring effective implementation of all activities for the all-round development of the watershed. Strong linkages have to be established with the related stakeholders for extending resources and facilities for effective implementation of the programme. Attempt was therefore made in the study to assess the extent of linkages established with various stakeholders. Sanghi and Rao (1982) emphasized the indifference approach of the local farmers and lack of participation in the programme as the greatest hurdle in the implementation of dryland technology. The farmers were found to revert back to their traditional systems, once the project support was withdrawn from them. Extension services did not keep pace with the requirements of the situation as the project advanced. According to Rodriguez et al. (2014) the watershed management involves diverse groups including farmers, state and central government institutions, quasi-government agencies and NGOs. Each group differs widely in objectives and

interests but together they shape the face of watershed development. Inter-Institutional Linkages in Watershed management is a multi-disciplinary and multi-institutional effort. Therefore, the crucial role of coordination and collaboration among various disciplines and institutions involved need be assessed. In this regard, the types of institutions and the way they relate to each other in providing synergy become crucial.

The watershed development programme implementation is much faster with participatory style and its effective implementation depends on expected private benefits, extent of farmers' participation and organization of farmers in small groups, good local leadership, existence and enforcement of rules for fair and equity. Naidu (1992) observed that low level of awareness was due to non-awareness to programme, caste and ethnic differences, bureaucrat's tendency to ignore the poor and in promoting participation, appropriate education, communication, persuasion and demonstrations were important factors in promoting development. Singh (2009) reported that the important barriers to people's participation in watershed programme are illiteracy and lack of awareness among the watershed users committee group, prejudice and discrimination against farm women by their male counterparts, factionalism, casteism, and heterogeneity of the watershed population. Chambers (1994) suggested that unless the stakeholders were involved in the whole process of a development project, including its problem identification phase, they were less likely to participate actively in implementation activities. Mascarenhas (1999) reported that basically there are two kinds of institutions that need to link and interact frequently with each other in watershed management – one involving the internal stakeholders and the other involving the external stakeholders. The first is at village or community level in the form of SHGs or water user groups and obviously, these need to be federated at the watershed level for providing a forum for collective action. Yadav *et al.* (2013) stated that, once a good linkage with the market or marketing channel will develop, infra-structure facilities will increase rationally. Where as, provision of long term loan at low rate of interest to the farmers of watershed area can help in increasing agricultural assets. Arora (2003) suggested that for better implementation of watershed development programmes, exposure to technologies, need based training, effective linkage, co-ordination with local institutions, minimization of information gap and regular quarterly review meetings by the implementation staff as well as steering committee are essentially required which could be considered on priority basis. Poonia & Singh (2004) stated that there is a need to improve the existing level of technology; linkage between research, extension and farmer training, appreciation of farmers, flow of credit, post harvest technology for ensuring stability in return as well as sustained growth and employment in watershed areas. Kulshresth *et al.* (2014) studied the Budhara micro watershed in Ambah block of Morena district of Madhya Pradesh and concluded that Better co-ordination between development agencies and voluntary organizations is essential for effective implementation of watershed programme that Better co-ordination between development agencies and voluntary organizations is also essential for effective implementation of watershed programme. Rao & Reddy (2004) stated that farmers had medium participation in watershed projects. They had comparatively high participation at implementation stage and very low at pre-project stage. Big farmers have comparatively more participation than small and marginal farmers. Choudhury (1986) observed that traditional attitude and illiteracy were the main hurdles for the rural Poor's involvement in small scale watershed projects.

Jat *et al.* (2008) in their study on the Gaudi Palasia Micro Watershed situated in Indore district stated that better co-ordination between development agencies and voluntary organizations is also essential for effective implementation of watershed programme. The lack of effective co-ordination among project officials, agriculture extension department, agriculture research station and farmers is a constraint in the adoption of watershed technique. According to the

study undertaken by Bandaragoda (2005) there is a natural tendency of local stakeholders to readily provide local knowledge, information, and participate in action planning for developing appropriate strategies, as long as they are convinced that the efforts are for their own interests. Farmers' progressivity, excellence, and success are typically influenced by a variety of separate influences, or determinants. The actual components are latent dimensions of multiple underlying variables. Therefore, a focus on quantitative research was made in the current study with the intention of identifying and prioritising the determinants of farmers' socioeconomic characteristics that influence progressiveness, resulting in higher adoption and, higher profit and overall success of watershed activities. This was done in order to have such a perspective of the farmers as well as other stakeholders (Rakesh Kumar *et al.*, 2015). Socioeconomic status (SES) is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic access to resources and social position in relation to others. When analyzing a family's SES, the household income, education and occupation are examined, as well as combined income, whereas for an individual's SES only their own attributes are assessed (Udiin *et al.* 2014).

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a multivariate technique that analyzes a data table in which observations are described by several inter-correlated quantitative dependent variables. Its goal is to extract the important information from the table, to represent it as a set of new orthogonal variables called principal components (Abdi *et al.* 2013). Principal component analysis, or PCA, is a dimension reduction technique and a statistical procedure that allows us to summarize the information content in large data tables by means of a smaller set of "summary indices" that can be more easily visualized and analyzed. Principal Component Analysis, or PCA, is a dimensionality-reduction method that is often used to reduce the dimensionality of large data sets, by transforming a large set of variables into a smaller one that still contains most of the information in the large set.

A sequence of observations of possibly correlated variables are converted into a set of principal component values, which are variables that are linearly uncorrelated, in the statistical procedure known as principle component analysis (PCA). The principal components are eigenvectors of the data's covariance matrix. Thus, the principal components are often computed by eigen decomposition of the data covariance matrix or singular value decomposition of the data matrix. PCA is the simplest of the true eigenvector-based multivariate analyses and is closely related to factor analysis as reported by (Chachlakis, 2019). According to (Vyas & Kumaranayake, 2006). In mathematical terms, from an initial set of 'n' correlated variables, PCA generates uncorrelated indices or components, where each component is a linear weighted combination of the initial variables. The weights for each principal component are given by the eigenvectors of the correlation matrix, or if the original data were standardized, the co-variance matrix. The variance for each principal component is given by the eigenvalue of the corresponding eigenvector. The components are ordered so that the first component (PC₁) explains the largest possible amount of variation in the original data. The second component (PC₂) is completely uncorrelated with the first component, and explains additional but less variation than the first component, subject to the same constraint. Subsequent components are uncorrelated with previous components; therefore, each component captures an additional dimension in the data, while explaining smaller and smaller proportions of the variation of the original variables.

Objective

The study was undertaken with an objective to analyse and identify the socio economic variables of the respondents, affecting the degree of linkage, co-ordination and involvement of different stakeholders of Watershed development programme and by using of principal component analysis (PCA) to identify essentially

significant , socio economic variables . The knowledge and adoption level of the farmers depend upon the farmer's age, education, size of holding socio- economic status and their progressiveness because progressive outlook motivates the farmers to adopt the new ideas or agricultural technology for their economic gains. This study aims to categorize and focus on the dynamics of socio- economic characteristics in influencing the extent of linkage and coordination level of different watershed stakeholders operating in the study area. Specifically, in this study ,principal component analysis (PCA) was executed for necessary data reduction and cluster analysis to identify typical , socio economic variables affecting better establishment of functional linkages and effective coordination of the farmers with stake holders and implementing agencies involved in the watershed development programme .

Materials And Methods

The Western Undulating Agro-climatic Zone of Odisha, which includes the districts of Nuapada and Kalahandi, is where the study was conducted. The two district Kalahandi and Nuapada under Western Undulating Agro-climatic zone of Odisha have been selected for the study as draught is the common phenomena and tribal people mostly suffered from foodand nutritional in- security. Moreover, these districts had more number of watersheds in comparison to other districts. Hence; both the districts have been selected purposively for the study. For the investigation, six watersheds were chosen from two blocks in each district. A total of 192 people were chosen as responses, including the watershed president, secretary, chairman, six members of the user group, three people from the landless and women categories, and one member of the watershed committee for each watershed. With score values of 2, 1, and 0, respectively, the data obtained on the scale points of strongly agree, agree, and disagree were evaluated. The socio economic scale developed by (Trivedi ,1963) was used to measure the independent variables, including caste, education, land ownership, social involvement, and socioeconomic level .Mean score, gap percentage , Spearman's co relation (P), multiple regression analysis and Principal component analysis (PCA) were employed to reveal the results . Principal component analysis was used for necessary data reduction analysis and it was evident from our results that various socioeconomic factors define clusters and can be associated with knowledge level of the respondents and adoption level of watershed practices .

Table – 1 : Comparative analysis of support from the stakeholders (n = 192)

Sl. No.	Support	Mean Score			Pooled mean score (n = 192)	Gap (%)
		Nuapada district (n = 96)	Kalahandi district (n = 96)	Diff. (%)		
1	Community organization	1.55	1.67	7.19	1.61	46.33
2	Technical guidance	1.27	1.49	14.77	1.38	54.00
3	Credit and finance	0.70	0.92	23.91	0.81	73.00
4	Input supply	0.70	1.12	37.50	0.91	69.67
5	Infrastructure development	0.98	1.13	13.27	1.06	64.67
6	Policy consideration	1.50	1.29	14.00	1.40	53.33
	Average	1.12	1.27	18.44	1.20	60.17

(Maximum obtainable Score – 3)

Comparative analysis of data revealed from the table indicated that significant gaps were observed on the support of the various stakeholders associated with the implementation of the Watershed Development Programme. Maximum gap of 73.00% were observed on the supports towards credit and finance followed by input supply (69.67%), infrastructure development (64.67%), technical guidance (54.00%), policy consideration (53.33%) and community organization (46.33%). The findings may conclude that the Watershed Development Programme was not implemented as per the guideline for which the District Watershed Advisory Committee need to sufficiently exposed the project officials and watershed

Prior to proceeding with the PCA approach, the Bartlett's test (Bartlett, 1950) and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy were performed to evaluate the appropriateness of the variables to be used as inputs to the PCA approach (Field , 2009). The Bartlett's test of sphericity checks the null hypothesis that the inter-correlation matrix came from a population in which the variables to be used in the PCA are all non-collinear . The results from this test using the survey data revealed a significant test (Chi-square = 863.523 and p -value = 0.000) suggesting that the variables are uncorrelated and hence suitable for a PCA. On the other hand, the KMO test compares the correlations and the partial correlations between the variables with a small KMO suggestive of highly correlated data. Using the Kaiser (1974) characterization of the KMO values revealed that the study's KMO statistic of 0.748 is middling and suggestive of less correlated data. which all support the appropriateness of the analyzed data for the multivariate analysis procedures. The PCA approach followed the Kaiser criterion of retaining all the components with eigenvalues greater than one (1). Also, to simplify the interpretability of the PCA results, the components were rotated, using the Kaiser's normalization applicable when the number of variables does not exceed 30, which is the case with the analyzed data. This approach has also been applied in recent and related studies (Bidogeza et al.2009) and (Nainggolan et al. 2013). All the statistical analysis was conducted in SPSS version 19.0 and results were described in different sub heads .

Results And Discussion

People in rainfed areas counter daunting natural conditions by following traditional and low risk cultivation practices that typically yield low returns. The watershed development must lead to people's self reliance, self support and self esteem. Land use adjustment is vital to the implementation of watershed programmes. Meaningful and effective adjustment can be achieved through organizing people's institutions and people's action. Therefore, the stakeholders have significant contribution in effective implementation of the programme towards up liftment of the watershed people. Attempts have been made for a comparative analysis of the support extended by various stakeholders involved in the implementation of Watershed Development Programme. The results obtained from the analysis of pooled mean score value have been presented in table below.

beneficiaries on the guideline and closely monitor for the involvement of all the stakeholders for successful implementation of the programme. One of the best examples of effective implementation of any programme is that where people feel a sense of ownership over the programmes. Strong linkages have to be established with the related stakeholders for extending resources and facilities for effective implementation of the programme. Attempt was therefore made in the study to assess the extent of linkages established with various stakeholders. The data collected from the respondents on scale point of strong, moderate and no linkage have been analysed and presented in table below.

Table – 2 : Extent of linkage with the stakeholders

Sl. No.	Stakeholder	Nuapada district (n = 96)	Rank	Mean Score			Spearman's rho (ρ) Value	Pooled mean score (n = 192)	Rank
				Kalahandi district (n = 96)	Rank	Diff. (%)			
1	Revenue department	1.03	IV	0.84	VI	18.45	0.78**	0.94	III
2	Electricity department	0.27	X	0.33	IX	18.18		0.30	VIII
3	Agriculture department	1.57	II	1.30	II	17.20		1.44	II
4	Soil conservation department	1.74	I	1.66	I	4.60		1.70	I
5	Horticulture department	1.57	II	1.30	II	17.20		1.44	II
6	Agriculture Engineering department	0.41	VIII	0.20	X	51.20		0.30	IX
7	Credit institutions	0.82	V	0.99	V	17.17		0.91	IV
8	Cooperative department	0.35	IX	1.21	III	71.07		0.78	V
9	Traders and input dealers	0.55	VI	0.53	VIII	3.64		0.54	VII
10	Animal resource department	0.13	XI	0.10	XI	23.08		0.12	X
11	Research institutions	0.50	VII	0.73	VII	31.50		0.62	VI

(Maximum obtainable Score – 2)

** Significant at 0.01 level of probability

The data in the table revealed that the respondents of both Nuapada and Kalahandi districts were agreed for the good linkage with Soil Conservation, Agriculture and Horticulture Departments. The respondents of Kalahandi district though agreed for the linkage with cooperation department which were not agreed by the respondents of Nuapada district. Poor opinions were also observed towards linkage with all other departments mentioned in the table.

The rank order correlation being significant, it is inferred that the difference between the two groups of respondents from two districts is valid. The respondents of the two districts differed in their opinions on extent of linkages established as observed through Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

Watershed Development Programme aimed at the development of the watershed as a whole. The beneficiaries having land may get the benefits from the Agriculture, Horticulture and Soil Conservation Departments. The landless people need the support of animal Resource and other departments. Linkage with traders and input

dealers ensure timely supply of inputs, credit institutions for financial assistance, research institute for capacity building and technology generation, cooperation department for subsidy and marketing of the produce, Agriculture Engineering for farm mechanization, revenue department for plantations and fodder development in Government land for the landless and resource poor as well as electricity department for power supply towards farm activities. It is therefore suggested that the project officials have to liason with all these departments and establish good linkage for adequate support ensuring effective implementation of all activities for the all-round development of the watershed.

Further attempt have been made for the multiple regression analysis to find out the important socio - economic variables of the respondents exhibiting influence towards linkage with stakeholders. The results obtained from the analysis of data have been reflected in table below.

Table-3:-Influence of socio -economic variables influencing linkage on Stake holders (n=192)

Variable	Un standardized Co-efficient		Standardized Co-efficient		't' value	Probability
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta	Std. Error		
Age (X1)	0.363	2.303	0.009	0.068	0.157	0.874
Education (X2)	2.469	1.386	0.146	0.059	1.780	0.076
Family type (X3)	1.816	3.074	0.039	0.032	0.590	0.555
Family size (X4)	5.728	3.041	0.128	0.066	1.883	0.061
Social participation (X5)	0.238	0.685	0.022	0.049	0.347	0.728
Cosmopolitaness (X6)	0.196	0.489	0.030	0.057	0.401	0.688
Extension contact (X7)	1.518	0.491	0.254	0.033	3.087	0.002
Communication material used (X8)	0.807	0.618	0.119	0.023	1.305	0.193
Type of house(X9)	-1.796	2.201	-0.069	0.054	-0.816	0.415
Land holding (X10)	4.141	1.953	0.193	0.063	2.120	0.035
Occupation (X11)	-5.276	2.533	-0.130	0.084	-2.082	0.038
Annual Income(X12)	2.070	2.038	0.102	0.057	1.015	0.311

R2:0.408, Adj R2=0.368, SE=17.235

As observed from the table, the best fitted regression equation could explain 40.80% of the total variance in influencing the support of the stakeholders. Among twelve variables, education, family size,

extension contact, holding size and occupation helps in exhibiting positive influence on the stake holders extending

PCA data analysis and results and discussions

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.777
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	863.523
	Df	78
	Sig.	.000

The results from the KMO and Bartlett sphericity test showed that the variables under study are related justifying the use of PCA. A total number of 12 variables from 192 respondents were included in

PCA study and ,the overall KMO was greater than 0.5 (0.777), while the Bartlett's sphericity test was significant (p -value = 0.000).

Table 5 : Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Communalities

Communalities		
Variables	Initial	Extraction
Age (X1)	1.000	.647
Education (X2)	1.000	.574
Family type (X3)	1.000	.522
Family size (X4)	1.000	.468
Social participation(X5)	1.000	.520
Cosmopolitaness (X6)	.615	.615
Extension contact (X7)	.701	.701
Communication material use (X8)	.679	.679
Type of house (X9)	.733	.733
Land holding (X10)	.395	.395
Occupation (X11)	.761	.761
Annual Income(X12)	.493	.493

The communalities are computations of the extent to which a variable is explained by the components. Communalities is the total amount of variance on original variable shares with all other variables included in the analysis . PCA assumes that total variance of the original variables can be explained via the components and uses as starting values for the Communalities 1.0. Communalities is the proportion of each variable's variance that can be explained by the factors (e.g., the underlying latent continua). It was observed that Occupation (X11) has the highest communality, followed by the variables Type of house (X9), Extension contact (X7), Communication material use (X8), Cosmopolitaness (X6), Age (X1) and Education (X2) has the highest communalities . The variable Land holding (X10) has the lowest communality indicates that it is less well explained by the analysis than any of the other variables . However, the factor loadings or component loadings for the PCA are larger in absolute values than the communalities, and as a result, the total variance explained is likewise larger. Factor loadings for the PCA are the correlations between a certain observed variable and a particular factor. Higher levels indicate a closer bond. The PCA defines communality as the sum of all influences on a single observed variable from all of its connected components. It is the same as R² in multiple regressions and equals the sum of all squared factor loadings for all factors associated to the observed variable. The value ranges from zero to 1 where 1 indicates that the variable can be fully defined by the factors and has no uniqueness.

Fig I : Scree plot for identifying the number of components

The eigenvalue is plotted against the factor number in a scree plot. It is seen that these values in the first three columns of the table immediately above. From the fourth factor onwards, we can observe that the line is almost flat, meaning the each successive factor is accounting decreasing percentage of the overall variance.

The following scree plot shows the number of Eigenvalues (λ) from the example shown on the main principal components analysis, ordered from biggest to smallest. In PCA the Kaiser criterion eliminates the components whose eigenvalues are less than 1, (when the data is standardized). Greater than '1' eigenvalue

suggests that the corresponding component explains more variance than a single variable, given that a variable accounts for a unit of variance. A widely recognized criterion is called the Kaiser-Guttman rule (Kaiser, 1960) and simply states that the number of factors is equal to the number of factors with eigenvalues (λ) greater than 1.0. From the above Scree plot it was evident that only the first three components had eigenvalues (λ) greater than 1.00 and together these explained 57.33 % of the total variability in the data. Thus we concluded that a three factor solution will probably be adequate.

Table 6 : Rotated Component Matrix (Extraction Method)

Rotated Component Matrix			
	Component		
	1	2	3
Land holding (X10)	.842		.158
Annual Income(X12)	.822		.280
Type of house (X9)	.808	.102	.124
Cosmopolitaness (X6)	.476	.392	-.374
Education (X2)	.260	.753	-.109
Communication material use (X8)	.351	.726	-.224
Social participation(X5)		.677	
Extension contact (X7)	.502	.567	-.205
Age (X1)	-.138	.542	.181
Family type (X3)	.109		.750
Family size (X4)	.239	.157	.663
Occupation (X11)			.623

*Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization*

In the rotated factors, the variables like Land holding , Annual Income, Type of house, Extension contact and Cosmopolitaness all have high positive loadings on the first component and the variables like education, communication materials use, social participation extension contact and age have high positive loading in second component and variables like Family type, Family size and occupation have high positive loading in third component . Studies have shown that cosmopolitaness strongly correlates with the

effectiveness of extension materials use by (Malathesh et al. 2009).The eigenvalue (variance) for each principal component indicates the percentage of variation in the total data explained. Only factor loadings of 0.3 or more were considered significant as earlier reported by Gorsuch (1974) Looking at the above the values more than 0.4 were highlighted , states the high loadings for each factor and that is they seem to appear logical.

Table – 7 : Extraction Method: Total Variance Explained by Principal Component Analysis

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.120	31.695	31.695	4.120	31.695	31.695	3.058	23.520	23.520
2	2.082	16.018	47.713	2.082	16.018	47.713	2.600	19.998	43.518
3	1.251	9.620	57.333	1.251	9.620	57.333	1.796	13.814	57.333
4	.998	7.678	65.011						
5	.862	6.630	71.640						
6	.729	5.609	77.249						
7	.673	5.177	82.426						
8	.548	4.217	86.643						
9	.498	3.831	90.474						
10	.412	3.168	93.642						
11	.366	2.818	96.460						
12	.269	2.071	98.531						
13	.191	1.469	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Here we have extracted three (3) principal components from the above table 7 . However the factor loadings or the component loadings for the PCA are larger in absolute values as are the communalities and as a consequence the total variance explained is also greater. Factor loadings for the PCA is equal to correlation between a specific observed variable and a specific factor. Higher values mean a closer relationship. The PCs were ranked according to

the original variance they explained ie PC 1 will explain the most important component, and PC2 the second most and so on. The Kaiser Rule is the most popular method for determining the number of components, and most systems use it by default. As the total number (12) of variables were considered for the factor analysis and according to Kaiser's(1958) criterion was followed to retain only those factors with Eigen values (λ) > 1.00, hence a

total of three factors all having Eigen values >1.00 have been reported in the above Table. The more variables that load onto a particular component (i.e., have a high correlation with the component), the more important the factor is in summarizing the data. An eigenvalue (λ) is an index that indicates how good a component is as a summary of the data.

In PCA simply selecting the Eigen values (λ) greater than 1 is considered as Principal component and in this study, only the first three components have eigen values over 1.00 and together these explained over 57.33% of the total variability in the data. The first component (comp 1) could be explained by five socio-economical variables, viz. Land holding, Annual Income, Type of house, extension contact and Cosmopolitanism as indicated in table 6, by the communality values of 0.842, 0.822, 0.808, 0.502 and 0.476 respectively. It was considered that farmers with and larger land holdings with higher income levels having more extension contact with cosmopolite in nature make an effort to keep good rapport and linkage and better co-ordination with different stake holders and developmental department associated with watershed development activities. Farmers who own more land are considerably better equipped to accurately diagnose farming-related issues and identify creative strategies to address them by keeping close contact and good linkage with implementing agencies. The most variance (23.52%) in the overall variability of the data was contributed by this element, which was referred to as "Big and progressive farmers". In this context, it was important to note that there are several extension agencies, both governmental and private, to meet the informational, financial, and input needs of farmers. Good socio-economic status acts as supplementary factor to influence state of motivation regarding good earnings as reported by (Singh et al. 2009). "Similar findings were reported by (Lwayo and Maritim, 2003), stated that there was significant relationship between land size, age and education with the farmer's decision to adopt technologies in farm forestry. "The age of the farmer affected the farmer's knowledge and the awareness of the activities in the surrounding environment among other farmers." Similar findings were reported by (Gautam et al. 2020) and it was revealed that socioeconomic characters like education, caste, size of holding, social participation, socioeconomic status, and annual family income were positively and significantly correlated with attitude scores towards intervened technology. However, those farmers who have the particular quality of cosmopolitanism tend to get more benefit from these agencies. Studies have shown that cosmopolitanism strongly correlates with the effectiveness of extensions use by (Malathesh et al. 2009). Thus, we can say (comp-1) represents 'Big and progressive farmers' with high extension contact and it implies that households with relatively large farm sizes are more likely higher farm income, more cosmopolite in nature and keep good linkage and rapport and good contact with developmental agencies, acquires more need based information about the project activities.

The second component (comp 2) comprised five variables, namely Education (0.753), Communication material use (0.726), Social participation (0.671), Extension contact (0.567) and age (0.542) communality values (h^2) respectively. The variables as mentioned clubbed together, clearly depicting that they have high degree of inclination to keep good linkage and co-ordination with various developmental departments involved in implementation of watershed development activities. Education, social involvement, contact with extension agents, and the use of communication tools are all crucial factors that help farmers accept more information regarding guidelines and operational procedure of watershed activities by obtaining effective linkage and association with implementing agency. The second-highest variance (19.99%) in the overall data variability was given by the element known as "education and extension contact." Thus (comp 2) represents the young, educated experienced and innovative and progressive farmers. Age of the farmer and social participation with high extension contact are

important factor in the pursuit of state of economic motivation with risk motivation and it pursues towards high economic motivation by keeping good relation and involvement with the developmental departments involved in watershed activities.

The third component (comp 3) comprised three variables namely Family type (0.750), Family size (0.663) and occupation (0.623) as communality values. Family type and family size and farming as primary occupation are found to be more important attributes that lead to success of a farmer to engage in farming for higher income by adopting new technologies in more scientific manner by gathering farm related new innovation and keeping good linkage with implementing agencies. The factor termed as "farming occupation" and it contributed the third highest (13.814%) variance in total data variability. From the table 7, it was revealed that, Component 1 contributes 23.52% variance in and Component 2 contributes 19.99% variances followed by Component 3 which contributes only 13.81% of variances in dependent variable, the level of linkage and keeping co-ordination with watershed development and implementing agencies. Total variance explained in this case was 57.33%, this indicates the amount of the variability in the data has been modeled by the extracted factors.

Clearly the component 1 of the initial solution is much more important than the second component. However, in the right hand part of the table, the eigen values (λ) and percentage of variance explained for the three rotated factors are depicted. Whilst, taken together, the three rotated components explain just the same amount of variance (57.33%) as the three components of the initial solution, the division of importance between the three rotated factors is very important. The effect of rotation is to spread the importance more or less equally between the three rotated factors. It was noted that in the above table the eigen values (λ) of the initial solutions of component are 4.12, 2.08 and 1.25 compared to eigen values (λ) 3.05, 2.80 and 1.79 in the rotated factors.

Conclusion

First, three components were found by principal component analysis, which was used to reduce the data to just over 57.33 percent of its total variability. According to the study's findings, three main factor "Big and progressive farmers", "educated and extension contact" and "farming occupation" were discovered to have significantly high influence and contributed 23.52%, 19.99%, and 13.81% variance in determining the extent of farmers' functional linkage and co-ordination level with watershed implementing agencies and with other stake holders. It was concluded that multivariate analysis (principal component analysis) were useful tools for identifying important socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers that influence their linkage and co-ordination with stake holder by understanding and compliance with guidelines and technologies, as well as their full participation in the various watershed practices. The findings led to the conclusion that the project's officials must keep good linkage and co-ordination and rapport with the watershed's group members for effective implementation of the watershed program's to ensure the project's overall development. Good linkage with related stakeholders, regular meeting for exploring external resources and emphasis on solving problems were the major suggestions under policy considerations.

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